

Evolving Depictions of Environmental Sustainability: A Comparative Study of two Documentaries

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Abstract

When it comes to claim rights and Freedoms there as citizens and as Nations or Actors within the context of international Arena we consider ourselves as the citizens of the world as said by a cosmopolitan philosopher namely Diogenes. However, when it comes to the question of accountability and responsibilities there we rely upon CBDR (Common but differentiated Responsibility), North-South Divide, or Global south perspective and its counter narrative. The study wants to expose the double standards opted at individual level as well as at collective level by individual citizens and State Actors and Non-State Actors respectively. The question is about planet earth its quality and potential to sustain the future generations. Therefore, the study wants to bring one's attention towards the concept of sustainability, Global environment and awareness regarding its protection as our prime Responsibility.

Keeping in view the importance of the sustainable environment and concept of green economy, Nations who show their genuine concern towards sustainability, said Nations have evolved the Depictions of this sustainability in both forms viz textually as well as visually. One such mechanism is to showcase the Documentaries and Films via cinematic way.

Present study undertakes this task of comparative study of the evolution of sustainability Depictions and Storytelling imbued with framing theory and methodology.

The prime focus of the current study will be upon two documentaries, i.e., Riding solo to the top of the world & Koru Rajee the land of diggers.

in which it will be analysed that to what extent our approach towards depictions changed and evolved.

Finally, the study wants to suggest and respond the question of what type of economy we should prefer? GREEN or Economy after producing emissions

Keywords: Environmental Sustainability, Documentary Cinema, Framing Theory, Green Economy & Global Environmental Responsibility

1. Introduction

The concept of sustainability is a contested concept and is accordingly placed at the intersection of environmental law, Developmental economics, and public policy especially the climate policy. Since people from the Global South claim that they have less responsibility due to being the developing countries. Nations across the globe have long grappled with how to handle emissions, while maintaining environmental sustainability and accountability. Even though the idea of sustainability existed in traditional societies, but its history can be traced back only after the industrial revolution of the 18th & 19th century. This period triggered the first environmental awareness movements. Sustainability is basically based upon the idea of intergenerational equity, in which nations should act as protective parents, prioritising a balance between economic development, social equity, and environmental protection. Legal frameworks try to impact the technologically driven states, in which provisions were put into motion to control the State activities that are against the concept of green economy and healthy environment. However weak implementation and lack of awareness about these policies and legal frameworks led to the decay of the sustainability.

As of present scenario there were still some Nations who show reluctance towards the accountability and shifts the onus upon one another. But this article wants to convey this message to the public at large that we can't justify one wrong by another wrong. Although humankind as a whole now appears to be living well above the earth's carrying capacity, the ecological footprints of individual states vary to an extraordinary extent. Indeed, if everyone were to enjoy the current lifestyle of those in the developed countries more than three additional planets would be required.

International standards like the United Nations convention on sustainability, such as United Nations Framework convention on climate change (1992), Kyoto Protocol (1997), Paris Agreement (2015), Convention on Biological Diversity (1992), Montreal Protocol (1987), Agenda 21(1992), Sustainable Development goals (2015), which strongly oppose the emissions, degradation etc. Their focus is upon the global environmental problems, collectively promote International cooperation, legal and policy frameworks, encourage Sustainable economic and social development and protect natural resources for future generations. Awareness about the sustainability and evolution of Depictions via media, cinematic is being analysed by way of a comparative study of two documentaries i.e. Riding Solo to the Top of the World & Kora Rajee the land of diggers. with special attention paid to the approach change of the film industry with regard to the selection of sustainability based teams and frames to showcase the importance of Sustainable development goals. It examines the degree to which these frameworks are consistent with current scientific knowledge, empirical data on results, and United Nations commitments. It suggests the way forward to excel into development and sustainability together, without impacting environment and sustainability. By looking at these two significant documentaries, the study highlights the larger need to promote sustainability around the globe and finally promotes putting global environment ahead of National economy in order to improve public safety and collective welfare.

2. Statement of problem

Despite International Agreements like the United Nations conventions on sustainability, legal frameworks and protocols that are binding states to start a minimum or lowest per capita greenhouse gas emissions, yet few countries contribute as largest sources of GHG globally when accounted in total tones. The lack of a widely accepted “Appropriate” Norms and international political pressure to appear “Tough on environmental problems and crimes against the Mother earth” have resulted in policies at national levels that very often contradict with U.N standards and Norms. This continuous to develop well into the mid-20s and 21th century.

This paper focuses on two main issues: Under what legal circumstances is it appropriate to trial Nations at NGTs (National green tribunals) and at what level of environmental degradation from their part should that country be held strictly liable. The study specifically investigates how contemporary films and Documentaries map environmental sustainability

discourses from bio-centric perspective and Analyses the shift from Anthropogenic approach to eco centric approach. The study also focusses upon the environmental activism and strategies used by the young youth and activists to highlight the environmental sustainability, need of eco growth etc. The study also wants to study how policy think tanks are crafting policies and schemes in line with sustainability development goals and what steps are being taken by the Governments at national levels and what major international initiatives are there at place to push towards sustainability.

3. Objectives of the study

The purpose of this study is to do a comparative analysis of two different Documentaries, with regard to the evolution of sustainability Depictions, environmental protection, responsibility and accountability. Also the study wants to compare the changing film narratives from individual focus to community focus. It specifically looks at the environmental ethics and underpinning, its historical development and present position within the cinema and Alternatively the study wants to study that what is the present legislative frameworks as of 2026 that govern the global environmental protection.

The study also examines the parallel, discrepancies and underlying justifications in how well states in global south handle this responsibility.

This study also analysis the empirical data with regard to documentaries and films. Additionally, it assesses how well national policies with regard to sustainability practices adhere to international Norms, particularly united Nations conventions on sustainability. Lastly the study offers suggestions for improving green economy based on cost-benefit analysis.

4. METHODOLOGY

The evolution of sustainability Depictions in the cinema are examined in this paper using content-analysis method a qualitative method of research. Also the study relied upon the comparative research technique with multidisciplinary integration with environmental law cum science, developmental economics and public policy.

However, for the accomplishment of above specified objectives, the study does not rely on a single method or approach it demands the application of multiple methods, therefore it used descriptive and analytical study. Given the nature of the study, problem and method of data

collection, we have used historical, analytical and statistical method for analysis and interpretation of the data.

5. Environmental sustainability: Meaning and Nature.

According to the (United Nations Environment Program, n.d) (UNEP) environmental sustainability involves making life choices that ensure an equal if not better, way of life for future generation. Environmental sustainability aims to improve the quality of human life without putting much stress upon the earth's carrying capacity. It is about creating a balance between humans and the living world. This can be done in a way in which we should not waste and deplete natural resources unnecessarily. In simple terms environmental sustainability is the practice of interacting with the planet responsibly, to avoid depletion of natural resources and compromising the future generation's ability to meet their daily needs (inspire clean Energy, n.d)

Basically the concept of environmental sustainability came about as an effort to change the way of thinking about the planet Environmental sustainability is an offshoot effect of wider concept i.e. sustainable development. Behind this lies the reason for why the term development is now preferred rather than growth. It is because that growth is believed to be a quantitative increase while as development is believed to be a qualitative improvement which is not an island in itself rather it carries with other aspects like education, health and Equality.

Traditionally sustainability was a response to the ecological disaster but contemporary idea has been extended to every component of human life (Hajian & Jangchi Kashani, 2021)

5.1 Environmentalism: Philosophical Foundations.

According to McLuhan(1964), in Understanding media, There are no passengers on spaceship earth. We all are crew. Ecologism as a political ideology is based on the belief that nature is an interconnected whole embracing humans and non-humans, as well as the inanimate world. According to Bio-centric Equality principle, all organisms and entities in the ecosphere are of equal moral worth. (Heywood,2014a)

The term Environment in Sanskrit means Pasyavaran, literally meaning "Pariaavaran" means external covering. Hindu philosophy viewed man and environment as part and whole of the same thing. During Vedic period people used to worship the earth, sky, air, water etc. Even Sikh religion also insisted that human beings are composed of these elements. (Meenakshi, n.d)

Atharved discussed the purity and quality of water. Sages and rishi chants,” what of thee I dig out let that quickly grow over let me hit thy vital or thy heart “which means one can take from earth and atmosphere only so much one puts back to them. This is the most important present day principle sustainable development. (Meenakshi, n.d-b)

In Yajurveda respect for every form of life living as well as Non-living, consumption be based on Tyagaraja, its extreme exploitation of natural resources born on greed and profit be avoided, one's duty should be perform to avoid conflict disharmony and imbalance in the ecosystem. (Meenakshi, n.d-c)

As per the Bhargavat Gita & lord Krishna speaks about eternal truth or Santana Dharma. He compares the world to a banyan tree which has unlimited branches under which a species of animals, humans and life live. King Ashoka practised Buddhism, in which he practised that man should not overexploit natural resources too. Christians are baptized in water. Through Baptism in water Christians realizes that it is a sign of purification. In June 1972 Stockholm Declaration pope Paul IV in his message stated the “environment and resources are for everyone; they are inalienable property of everyone and there does not exist over this universal property discretionary sovereignty exempting from responsibility towards humanity of today and tomorrow (Meenakshi, n.d-d)

One more thing is Gaia Hypothesis developed by James Lovelock (1979,1989 and 2006). It advances the idea that the earth is best understood as a living entity that acts to maintain its own existence. Gaia theory suggests that the health of the planet matters more than that of any individual species presently living on it. (Heywood,2014b)

In contemporary times, environmental sustainability is an Arena of particular ideological and political debate.in the words of the early liberal English philosopher John Locke(1632-1704),human beings are “The masters and possessors of nature” However environmental thought is based on the principle of ecology, which primarily focuses upon the network of relationships that sustain all forms of life including human life. Current green politics encompasses two issues called as “reformist” ecology and” radical” ecology .Reformist ecology sometimes called as “Modernist “ecology clearly a form of humanist or Shallow

ecology. It seeks to reconcile the principle of ecology with central features of capitalist modernity. The watchword of this form of ecologism is sustainable development; especially what is called '*weak sustainability*' in economic terms after applying the cost benefit analysis modernist ecologists attempted to develop a balance between modernization and sustainability the chief ideological influence on this ecology is utilitarianism based on classical liberal thinking with prime focus upon "greatest happiness of greatest number (Heywood, 2014c)

Radical ecology by contrast view capitalist modernity, its values, structures and institutions, as the root cause of environmental degradation. Radical ecological perspective is also termed as social ecology that views Radical social change as the key to ecological sustainability. Deep ecology propounds that world should be understood strictly in terms of interconnectedness and interdependence, this involves rejecting all forms of anthropocentrism, and embracing egocentrism. (Heywood, 2014d)

Emergence of environmental activism: brief overview.

Environmental Activism is about to protect and defend the environment, to protest unjust and unsustainable resource uses, because of social, moral and environmental reasons Environmental activists may comprise and include indigenous people, peasants or fisher folks whose lives and livelihoods may be threatened by environmental change or dispossession, they may also include social movements, journalists etc. or any other entity who actively defend the environment because degradation has reached *for them*.to unacceptable levels.(UNEP 2018).Their vital role has recognized by the united Nations human rights council as *well*. *If we talk about COP26 the aim of united Nations was to "accelerate the measures towards the goals of the Paris Agreement and the UN framework convention on climate change. (Scheidel et al., 2020) According to Heidi, a young climate and environmental activist, who made a placard declaring "Reduce, Rise, Revolt & Climate Colonialism. Heidi view point is that there needs to be a visible change and that change can't be made merely by speaking or talking but by doing something on ground. Therefore, contemporary young environmentalists are vigorously condemning governmental greenwashing and injustices and are calling for a substantial change (Sloam et al., 2022)*

Economic and sustainable policies: Nexus and strategies

As we should have belief over that integrated policy strategies can help to achieve sustainable development while balancing adverse economic, social, and political impacts of *reforms*. At national levels every country is concerned about their GDP, PPP and, Per capita income of every individual should rise, overall poverty should come to decline. But at the same time we have to take into consideration the issue of sustainability therefore policy nexus, to accelerate green economy and develop green energy. Governments while crafting National development policies very often face challenges therefore it adds the responsibility of addressing the issue of implementation and finding out gaps. (Basheer et al., 2022)

Major international initiatives on the Environment are as :international convention for the regulations of whaling(1946),world meteorological organization (1950),Antarctic Treaty(1959),united Nations conference on the Human environment(1972),Convention on international trade in endangered species (1973),UN convention on the law of sea(1982),Vienna convention for the protection of ozone layer (1985),Brundtland commission Report(1987),Montreal Protocol (1987),international panel on climate change(1988),UN conference on environment and development(1992),Kyoto Protocol (1997),The UN climate change conferences held in Copenhagen, Durban & Doha(2009-12) etc. (McLuhan, 1964a). In our country India, government took various initiatives as well with regard to environmental sustainability such as climactic and sustainability e.g. Mission Life (lifestyle for environment), NAPCL(National Action Plan on climate change) etc. (The Prayas India, 2025). The country is rapidly scaling up its efforts in renewable energy investment, sustainable finance and green growth. India's top policy think-tank NITI Aayog is deeply concerned about united Nations sustainable development goals ((Earth5R, 2025a)

5.1 Environmental sustainability and climate policy of India.

With regard to climate policy ,India has made some bold commitments: Pledge to achieve net-zero carbon emissions by 2070. Governmental policies and schemes supporting sustainability in India are emerging as critical tools both at international and National levels. (Alteridge et al., 2012)

At the international level, India is emerging as a key factor in climate negotiations, while at the national and sub national levels, the climate policy landscape is becoming more ambitious. It is essential to unravel this complex landscape if we are to understand why policy looks the way it does, and the extent to which India might contribute to a future

international framework for tackling climate change as well as how international parties might cooperate with and support India's domestic efforts. (Frish, 2012)

The country, as a growing economic power, part of the G77 and China group and more recently in its cooperation with Brazil, China and south Africa as the BASIC group. India has among the world's lowest per capita greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, yet is the fifth largest source of GHG globally when accounted in total tones (Pew Centre 2008). India's emissions surged 65% between 1990 and 2005 and are projected to increase another 70% by 2020.

when compared to other major economies, India's emissions are low. India accounts for only 2% of cumulative energy-related emissions since 1850. On per capita basis, India's emissions are 70% below the world average and 93% below those of the united states. Being among the most vulnerable countries to climate impacts, India has a very real stake in negotiations reaching a meaningful outcome and a growing awareness of its own potential role in helping achieve such an outcome. Yet at home, the Indian government knows it must weigh these goals against other domestic priorities, particularly the push to achieve high levels of social and economic development including reducing poverty. (Guerrero, 2018)

Recent years have seen a shift in India's approach to negotiations within the United Nations framework convention on climate policy action in the national and subnational arenas. This trend toward a "Multi-level governance" situation, with a more independent sub-national dimension, makes it important to study the forces that are driving and shaping policy at each level. The focus is not on the substance of the actions themselves, but on bringing to light what motivates and conditions their approach. (Klein, 2015)

To understand how India might move forward from here, it is useful to examine India's historical role in and positions taken earlier at the climate negotiations. In the initial years, India was among the pioneers of various crucial formulations that went on to define UNFCCC and Kyoto protocol, including the key formulation that while all nations and people were responsible for anthropogenic climate change, some were more responsible than others and that per capita national emissions constituted the best metric to represent the respective contribution of different nations as well as to determine their share of the burden towards its solution. This principle of "common but differentiated responsibility" or CBDR, embodied in the UNFCCC, has underpinned the Kyoto protocol and all climate negotiations, until very recently. The idea of CBDR now constitutes a firewall between developed and developing countries has been sharply contested. (Raghunandan, 2013)

India played an important role not only in insisting on developed nations shouldering the emissions reduction but also in undertaking independent scientific studies and analyses to counter attempts, notably by the U.S, to shift blame for anthropogenic GHG'S away from the fossil-fuel based power generation, transportation, industries and lifestyles of the global north to activities in the developing countries, such as paddy cultivation and animal husbandry accused of producing competing quantities of methane. (Earth5R, 2025b)

Cinematic Reflections of Eco-Consciousness and awareness.

Media has a great tendency, to shape and Reflect the societal imaginaries, to influence societal perceptions and to shape the future *possibilities*. *If* media has a potential to largely reflect Anthropocentric worldviews, these media also have, the potential to promote eco-centric perspective. In the context of Bio-centric perspective, study and analysis of media is *crucial*. As far as eco-literature is concerned it played a crucial role in shaping environmental consciousness but its adaptation in a cinematic style has paved a way towards powerful visual medium for expanding its impact. Cinematic reflections evolved to translate the environmental themes from text to screen. Analysing the cinematic representation will help us to identify the pros and cons, successes and limitations of cinematic representation in conveying, ecological sustainability messages. (Geslin, 2025)

Rise of eco-consciousness in the cinema shows that films are not only artistic expressions but also tools for raising awareness and inspiration towards collective responsibility. Cinematic representation advocated eco-literary values, it helped to narrow-down the gap between text and screen, between theory and practice and between culture, environment and cinema. Also it offers transformative suggestions that how storytelling can derive social and ecological progress. (Patel, 2025)

Comparative analysis of Riding solo to the top of the world (2006) & Koru Rajee the land of diggers (2006).

If there is paradise on the earth, it is here, it is here, it is here" Thus said Emperor Jahangir and his consort about enchanting natural wealth of Kashmir

This crown of India lies in the extreme North of India. The mountainous state is blessed with lofty snow, clad peaks, deep gorges, glaciers, lush green meadows and verdant valleys full of Chinar trees, beautiful silvery lakes, charming flora and fauna, making it a "Paradise on

Earth". It is an excellent base for leisure and adventurous holidays amidst breath taking scenery.

Jammu and Kashmir has a very rich history and a distinct culture where people of all faiths live in perfect harmony. It houses some of the most sacred temples, mosques, monasteries and caves. Kashmiri handicrafts are well known all over the world. The ancient tradition of crafting a paper machine, wood carving, carpet and shawl making etc. generates substantial amount of foreign exchange. The world's highest observatory is set in Hanle, Ladakh in 1999. A visit to this paradise, resplendent in nature's glory, will linger long in the memory of the visitors.

Gaurav Jani makes a solo motorcycle trek to the highest habitable place on earth, the Changthang Plateau in Ladakh, bordering China. This is a motorcycle adventure travel documentary showing a solo riders journey, different landscapes, cultures and societies. This documentary is basically made by the rider Gaurav Jani to capture real things, people, places and events. The documentary visualizer the silence of the nature and then let's the silence to speak about natural surroundings, environmental settings. It conveys the meanings and purpose of every small thing that is there in nature. The documentary aims to inform, inspire and raise awareness related to environmental.

If we talk about the themes around which the documentary revolves around are:

Environmental Awareness:-The documentary used the natural environment per-se as the background of entire narrative captured by the solo *rider.it* highlights both sides of the environment one without human interference and other with human interference, both are different because the impact of human intervention is a wakeup call towards the conservation of environment.

Cultural encounters: -Here the documentary displays various cultural settings, people belonging to various cultural groups and local communities. It highlights how natural landscape becomes the reason that helps one individual to sustain and nourish other indigenous communities their culture ,conduct *and Adaptability.it* also shows that how sustainable resource consumption and simple living is useful to conserve and preserve the environment.

Human-Nature relationship: -

The documentary Depicts the relationship between Humans and Nature in a beautiful way like it shows how difficult and harsh terrains, lush greenery along the trek and then water bodies coming out from mountains helps the solo-rider *to survive*. It means nature though silent is having a great potential to help the humans to survive. besides the documentary focuses upon that what should be the approach of humans while dealing with the nature that is to say it should be humane and sustainable approach.

As far as the sustainable Development goals are concerned the documentary displays number of sustainable development goals in its various scenes like the Depiction of vast natural landscapes, rivers, lakes, valleys, mountains and terrains, pleatues etc. Here we see SDG 13 i.e. climate Action is touched and SDG 15 i.e. life on Land. The documentary highlights importance of conservation, vulnerability of environment to climate change, remote villages and rural life i.e. SDG 1(no poverty), SDG 10 (Reduced inequalities), & SDG 11(Sustainable Communities) In these goals the rider conveys the message that we can survive even, if our resources are limited but the condition is our approach must be simple and sustainable. However, the documentary also depicts the uneven Development that reinforces the rural marginalisation.

Third the documentary touches SDG 16, & SDG 17, i.e. peace justice and Strong Institutions and partnerships for goals. The solo riders interaction with local people, cultural exchange without any conflict, the Hospitality of local people towards the *rider*.so it highlights the peaceful coexistence beyond borders .Fourthly the documentary views us the Broken roads, weather and isolation. Here it touches SDG 9 i.e. industry, innovation, and infrastructure.so we find the connectivity and accessibility issues, lack of sound infrastructure and development gaps in our remote regions. Fifthly solo riders trekking depicts the minimalist living with self-survival. Here it touches the SDG 12 i.e. responsible consumption. The solo rider practically shows us that how people with minimum resources and with a sustainable life style that leads to eco-consciousness. sixthly the documentary shows the wildlife and natural silence. Here it touches the SDG 15 i.e. life on Land e.g. in one shot it vividly depicted the undisturbed Habitat of rats and other biodiversity. Seventh the solo riders uses the road that touches different nations from the northern sides of India.so SDG 16 i.e. peace and global cooperation. Eighth the solo-rider while trying to reach his destination fixes some more canes

of fuel with his motorcycle. It highlights the dependency on fuel and question about sustainability of travel so it touches SDG 7 i.e. Affordable and clean energy.

Lastly After watching the documentary, going through the technique of visual storytelling about nature we got a realist and authentic feel where silence speaks and realism is being shown through wide angle landscape shots.

Kora Rajee (The land of diggers)2006.

The Kurukshetra word kora-raji is made up of Kora and raji. Kora means digging and raji means state. Thus the word kora-raji means the place or state dominated by land-diggers. Basically these kuruk-speaking tribal labourers went to Assam and North-Bengal to dig land prepare them for plantation and accordingly named these places in their own language.

Actually it was the British erstwhile who forced these labours to migrate from Jharkhand to Assam and North-Bengal. The producer and director of this documentary film depicted the plight and misery of these labourers who used to work in these tea gardens of Assam and North-Bengal. But due to the impact of international market when India lost the status of being the largest tea-exporter in the world. The market rates for Indian tea fall down, with the result the effect upon labourers worsened more.

The documentary vividly depicted the life of the tribals who were brought into the lands of kuru Region in Assam and North-Bengal. The people started to consider these lands as their mother-land and they worked very hard to sustain their survival in these lands. However due to the loss of marketability of tea, the factories and companies started treating these labourers malafidely.the factory owners stopped paying them, basic facilities of life, like health system, education system, minimum wages proper housing and other sustainable affordability's. They reduced them to a position of mere migrant workers with the result the labourers find themselves in a problem of identity crisis. The Assam govt denied them the status of being schedule castes and status of being tribes. The local militants started attacking them.one of the deadliest attack was done in 2003 in which 90 labourers were killed. The documentary depicted some tractor like school van and some hospital but these were in a deteriorated condition. The Boards and management system of these plantations started to da a malafide practice while engaging the B.A pass candidate there were backdoor entries and it resulted the protests and strikes by these aggrieved labourers.

The documentary was having good subject line and narrative to depict therefore it won the international film festival award.

As far as sustainable development is concerned it touched various goals, like lack of clean water, lack of good health facilities No Sanitation at all, lack of clean drinking water, as people were shown with pots and other containers waiting their turn to get little bit water to sustain themselves i.e. SDG 6.

Another thing is the labours were forced to work manually by their own hands, there was no energy available as such explicit. e.g. electricity Tools *etc.so* lack of sustainable energy SDG 7. The manual exploitation was rampant *there.as* far as crop cycle was concerned the land was reduced to produce the single crop I.e. tea being the cash *crop.it* resulted the increase of income of factory owners only and not of labourers. 2nd these unsustainable practices resulted the environmental damage SDG 12 and later on it worsened the climate as well Sdg 13. Though the film earned the award but it was more because of its Depiction of tribal crisis, cultural and identity crisis, not on the basic of Depiction of SDG goals.

So in comparison to Riding solo to the top of the world the documentary Kora rajee Depicted the cultural and identity crisis and former Depicted the travel adventure and natural landscapes northern India especially Ladakh Region.

Evolution of environmental dictation from Indian perspective.

Earth as a planet is considered as a sacred entity since ancient Indian civilisation. The sacred books like Vegas, purana and Upanishad highlighted the importance of nature and especially the earth, with the passage of time we trace other references from history from ancient down to modern period, the earth and its environment remained the Central focus. However, there took a shift from earth being sacred to being a resource as well as eco-logical life-line.

Currently the concept of sustainable environment is not limited only to our policy domain and academia, but the concept has landed into the cinema as well, the film makers. Producers, and directors started to highlight the issues and problems visually as well on digital platform. Furthermore, environment is not only a symbol of romanticism but also the issue to have a concern about. Till now so many films and documentaries were made in which focuses is upon the SDG goals, resource management and ecological balance.

Empirical results: sustainable development and green economy.

In comparison to traditional developmental models, the analysis and studies consistently demonstrate that sustainable development and green economy is being highly appreciated and focused. The studies show that the bank on emissions and transition due to the positive and green growth, the environmental risks reduced to a large extent. Key results show the investment in green initiatives and sustainable growth.

Compliance with international conventions, summits and treaties.

India is strongly committed to international standards and environmental protection related treaties. The constitution of India came up with provisions related with the environment, the policy domain of India back at home is in line with international rules and standards set by international community. India has entered into several bilateral Agreements, it ratified the treaties to protect the environment and boost the green economy. Key Compliance action includes the ratification of the Paris Agreement, active participation in UNFCCC party to Stockholm convention etc.

Limitation of the study

The study offers a through comparison of two documentaries viz Riding solo to the top of the world 2006 and Kora Rajee A land of diggers 2006.both the documentaries won awards on different pretext. The study is limited to analysis of films while highlighting the SDGs and depicting the environmental sustainability.

1. Jurisdictional and geographical scope: Indian cinema and Compliance with international conves to upheld the environmental sustainability.

2.Temporal restrictions: As of March 30, 2026 the study is based upon laws, rules, treaties, instances and statistics, that is there till now.

3.Methodological approach: The study mainly used the secondary sources and method is analytical and content *analysis method*. No primary source and fieldwork is included.

5.Interdisplinary depth: The study relied on synthesised study of displaces such as environmental law, Developmental economics and policy science.

These restrictions show chances for future research to expand the breadth and include original empirical data, but they also reflect conscious decisions made to guarantee analytical depth and concentration on the main issue.

Results and Discussion:

The comparative analysis shows that the two documentaries were based upon two different themes and stories, like Nature, culture, environment identity crisis, climate actions etc. The study shows how the SDGs are being touched and how the producers and directors of the two respective documentaries vividly depicted the environment into different shots and scenes.

Conformity to Developmental economics and policy science:

According to the modern concept of development the focus is on quality and sustainability the transition place from emission based traditional economy to green economy and clean energy.

Empirical results: sustainability and green economy: compared with traditional economy, it is seen from our policy decisions and initiatives, our country is largely and strongly committed with the goals of sustainability and green economy objectives. Increased green investment and setting of targets to achieve the long-term goals are being highly focused.

Compliance with international standards: India is party to so many treaties and conventions to show the common intention with regard to environmental sustainability, notably the policy landscape of India show the signs of resemblance and similarities with international standards in the field of environmental risk reduction and its protection

Conclusion

The present study concludes that environmental sustainability is not merely a theoretical or policy-driven concept but a shared global responsibility that transcends national, political, and economic boundaries. While nations often claim universal rights over resources and development, their reluctance to equally share environmental responsibilities exposes a persistent gap between commitment and action. This contradiction reflects the broader tension between economic growth and ecological preservation.

Through a comparative analysis of the documentaries *Riding Solo to the Top of the World* and *Kora Rajee: The Land of Diggers*, the study demonstrates a clear evolution in cinematic representations of sustainability from passive, nature-centric storytelling to more critical, socially engaged narratives highlighting environmental injustice, identity crises, and structural inequalities. The findings reveal that documentary cinema has emerged as a

powerful medium for shaping public perception, bridging the gap between policy discourse and ground realities, and fostering eco-consciousness.

The research further establishes that while international frameworks and national policies, particularly in India, show increasing alignment with sustainable development goals and green economy principles, challenges remain in implementation, accountability, and equitable distribution of environmental responsibilities. The principle of “common but differentiated responsibility” continues to influence global climate politics, often leading to contested interpretations and uneven commitments.

Importantly, the study emphasizes that a shift from anthropocentric to eco-centric approaches is essential for long-term sustainability. It advocates for a model of development that prioritizes environmental integrity alongside economic and social progress. The evidence suggests that green economy initiatives, sustainable policies, and increased environmental awareness supported by media and cinema can significantly contribute to reducing ecological degradation.

In conclusion, the study strongly supports the transition towards a green economy over emission-intensive developmental models. It calls for collective global action, stronger policy enforcement, and responsible individual behavior to ensure that environmental sustainability is preserved for future generations. The role of cinema, policy frameworks, and public awareness must work in tandem to create a more balanced, just, and sustainable world.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are put forth to change our approach towards the economic growth and environment, specifically with regard to the emission reduction standards, while focusing upon the comparative study and analysis of developmental economics, environmental law and policy science to reach out at sustainability as a way forward, for every country especially in India.

1. Minimize the emissions as much as possible.

Every country must put a cap on carbon emissions and must minimize the carbon emission threshold with strong preference over carbon free energy consumption.

2. Limit or eliminate routine use of CFCs, HFCs and other carbon producing agents. Except in the direst situations and need we should use Non-Renewable resources, otherwise we must

use only Revenuable or non-conventional sources of energy such as solar energy and other carbon free sources of energy so that while developing our green economy we will take care of environment as well as ecological balance and sustainability together.

3. Give Green Economy priority over Brown economy or Economy based on carbon emissions: -Funds must be diverted from investments in carbon based economy to green investments. Measure like public awareness programs, education and eco-consciousness must be developed among nations at large.

4. Align Domestic laws with international standards: -India should completely adopt the recommendations of United Nations Development program, United Nations program on sustainability and other rules that support sustainability and green investments.

5. Encourage public education and eco-consciousness. Environmental sustainability Depictions via media, films, documentaries must create awareness and must educate people about sustainability and SDGs. The consciousness about environmental sustainability must be developed so that the next-generation should enjoy the environmental sustainability as well.

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